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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	Long term reliability effects of proton irradiation on SiC MOSFETs
Project TA identifier	TA07-176
General application	Space, avionics
Type of test	SEE
Group leader, Institute	Kimmo Niskanen, JYU
Dates of the experiment	28/8/2023 - 1/9/2023
Facility	Proton irradiation facility, PSI
Amount of access granted	18 hours

Objectives of the experiments

This work focuses on the impact of proton irradiation on short and long term reliability degradation of the commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) silicon carbide (SiC) power MOSFETs, especially focusing on proton-induced single event burnout (SEB) and long-term reliability degradation due to the non-destructive radiation effects. Long term reliability degradation is studied by applying post-irradiation electrical stress on the devices. The effect of proton energy and fluence on the SEB sensitivity and latent damage is studied.

Experiment test report

The effect of proton energy on the SEB cross section and latent gate damage was investigated. The results obtained in this experiment will be compared with 50 MeV proton tests performed at RADEF and combined results will be presented in journal and/or conference paper. Early analysis suggests that the SEB cross section increases with increasing proton energy. Results are presented in Table 1 and Figure 1.

10-14 devices per run were irradiated in parallel configuration. DUT: Wolfspeed C3M0350120D Silicon Carbide Power MOSFET.

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Table 1. The bias and proton energy configurations

V_{DS} (V)	E_p (MeV)	SEB cross section (cm^2)	Flux ($\text{p s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$)	Fluence (p cm^{-2})
400	200	No SEBs	1e8	1e11
500	200	No SEBs	1e8	1e11
600	200	No SEBs	1e8	1e11
700	200	2.12e-12	1e8	1e11
800	200	5.81e-12	1e8	1e11
900	200	4.31e-11	1e8	1e11
1000	200	4.50e-10	1e8	3e10
700	100	No SEBs	1e8	1e11
900	100	1.42e-11	1e8	1e11
1000	100	7.09e-11	1e8	9e10

 Figure 1: SEB cross section as a function of V_{ds} for 100 MeV and 200 MeV proton energies

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

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As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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